

Historical Perspectives on Family Planning Policies and Practices: A Review of Global Trends

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ABSTRACT

Family planning is a multifaceted public health intervention and a sociocultural phenomenon. This study aims to explore the historical underpinnings of family planning policies and practices, tracing their evolution from early traditions to the complex global initiatives of the modern era, historical context, key trends, and diverse approaches employed across different regions and time periods, and to shed light on the multifaceted nature of the family planning as both a social and public health interventions. This research paper provides an analysis of the historical context and key trends that have shaped national family planning initiatives over time. The analysis reveals that family planning policy and practice have evolved over time from the early era to the present era. It also highlights the need for strengthening the healthcare infrastructure to deliver family planning services effectively. Despite progress in contraceptive usage and declines in unmet needs in several states, regional variations persist, underscoring the importance of targeted interventions to address specific challenges in different parts of India. Additionally, it is crucial to prioritize overcoming current obstacles and inequalities in order to attain widespread access to FP services and advance equity in reproductive health.

Keywords: Family planning, Public health, Policies and practices, Contraceptive, Health care infrastructure

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I. INTRODUCTION

Family planning, the conscious effort to regulate fertility and reproduction, has been a cornerstone of public health and social policy for centuries. This research delves into the historical underpinnings of family planning policies and practices, tracing their evolution from early traditions to the complex global initiatives of the modern era, historical context, key trends, and diverse approaches employed across

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